

Maritime Power

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The concept of naval prestige is illustrated by the Maritime Power. The example of the United States of America, the Russian Federation, and China, with their presence in the seas, proves this statement.

The configuration of Sea Power has ten requirements:

1 - Maritime Power shall be translated into international recognition of its effective value. This causes considerable influence on the solution of antagonisms.

2 - Maritime Power must include extensive merchant traffic with its own resources covering all markets, a condition of great importance to national economies.

3 - The Maritime Power must provide a permanent bond between the maritime nations, so as to ensure, both the mutual protection of their trade, the guarantee of uninterrupted use of the oceans through military alliances.

Great political-diplomatic sensitivity of the developed nations is needed to consent to a change in the status quo that has prevailed for centuries, allowing more rational participation of developing nations in maritime trade.

4. The Maritime Power must provide the necessary logistical support to wartime military forces, as well as to the economic life of the nation.

5 - The Maritime Power must exercise deterrence through the threat of massive destruction on the sea.

This qualification of the Maritime Power stems from the fact that the superpowers use or intend to use the sea for the installation or positioning of nuclear weapons systems in submarines for a deterrence action,

6 - The Maritime Power must be able to gather elements of appropriate value and long-term aerial surveillance in remote areas, so as to ensure effective control of those areas.

7 - The Maritime Power must present technological leadership in the development of ocean resources, aiming at commercial, political and military benefits.

8 - The Maritime Power must have a technological base that allows the construction and expansion of naval forces, if and when necessary.

9 - The Maritime Power should acquire prestige in the international scientific community by recognizing its authority in matters related to the sea.

These three requirements currently represent the greatest challenge for developing nations lack in financial resources and technical-industrial capacity.

10 - The Maritime Power shall provide capacity for isolated action at sea, in the fulfilment of national, political and economic interests.

The ability for unilateral action not only increases the number of military options but also makes political manoeuvring easier and more credible.

Naval Power - Historical Evolution

The classic naval strategic conceptions are based on the political-strategic and technological frameworks of the periods that served as their historical basis and the time in which they were formulated.

These conceptions also reflect the national interests and possibilities of the authors of their formulation.

Mahan's work, for example, derives from a historical framework characterized by colonialism, imperialism and technology that gave a decisive preponderance to big warships.

In the historical period studied by Mahan, superior naval power on ships could seriously affect the enemy, beating him in a decisive battle: the Sea domain, resulting from this victory, allowed the defeated maritime communications lines to collapse, leading to the collapse of colonial political-economic structure.

Mahan emphasized the strategic conception of the decisive battle and its material corollary, the constitution of the squadrons around the command ships.

The strategic design of the power squad is a decisive battle design tailored to meet the limitations of lower naval power. It also enhances large units, as a powerful squad must be able to destroy the enemy in a battle when it is not operating in a concentrated position.

In fact, a well-established and well-placed power squadron makes it possible for the superior Naval Power to rely on the Sea domain only if and where it can engage that squadron with superior forces; Sea domination is the desired effect as in the case of the design of the decisive battle.

French theorists were the first to realize the consequences of technological development in the late nineteenth and early twentieth century's (torpedoes, mines, steam turbines, and submarines).

The French ships' re-evaluation of the possibilities of the smaller ships was mainly influenced simultaneously by the perception of the implications of the new technology

and the national perspective of the strategic problem: for France, maritime communications were not as important as for England.

The Sea Domain was not so vital to him, except in restricted areas of more immediate interest (Algeria and Morocco, the main French colonies of that time, were relatively close to the metropolitan territory).

The strategic conceptions generated from this framework (deterioration and secondary operations conducted by large numbers of small, fast and well-armed ships) led at most to broadly navigating the Sea domain to the enemy and establishing the control in areas relatively close to base.

The French did not fail to attach value to the great ships and the decisive battle for special situations, particularly those concerning the confrontation between great maritime powers with world interests. But they differed from Mahan's work as they admitted the decision at sea along different paths from the decisive battle between squadrons surrounding the main ships.

It is curious to note that the strategic conceptions generated in times of political and technological instability, as was the case around 1900, are somewhat inaccurate in terms of conduct, objectives and instruments.

The French Young School, for example, presented nothing as precise as the conception of the decisive battle, which advocated the engagement of the main opposing forces, followed by the establishment and operation of the domain of the Sea.

In the first half of the twentieth century the great powers developed their Naval Power accordingly to the classical strategic conceptions, each power giving them a relative importance that depended on its specific naval problem and its possibilities.

England, the USA and Japan gave priority to the decisive battle, establishment and using the Sea domain.

The naval treaties in Washington and London reflect this priority, as they demonstrate the concern of these three powers with the large units; technological subterfuges aimed at alleviating the limitations of treaties, such as the installation of 18 "guns in the Yamato class," also indicate the high priority given to the decisive battle.

The doctrine of employment of Japanese submarines in the Second World War, which advocated attacking naval forces rather than maritime traffic, is part of the strategic conception of deterioration, but its purpose was ultimately to weaken enemy Naval Power to ease the task of the main forces in decisive battle. .

France and Italy have followed ensemble, although with more modest geographical ambitions. Italy, which had entered too late in the colonialist adventure, intended only to revive the “Mare Nostrum” in the Mediterranean.

Germany initially adopted a mixed conception: the squadron of World War I was designed for the decisive battle and rule of the North Sea, and for war and denial of Atlantic ruling, at a time when England and the coalition of France.

Russia seemed to be heading towards a situation of increasing antagonism, which favoured the emergence of the German Naval Power as the balance's supporter.

The events of the war showed the consequences of an incorrect political assessment of the preparation of naval power: the German squadron could not establish dominance of the North Sea, and its use as a potential squadron did not benefit Germany, as committed the British units as a sentinel of the German Squad.

After 1918, Germany moved more resolutely towards denial of the Sea domain due to the limitations of Versailles and the re-evaluation of its naval problem.

An important correlation between the sea and the changes in the political-strategic framework is that of the old concept of freedom of navigation of the seas.

The XXI Century

Modern technology allows the sea to be explored more broadly and intensely than was possible in the past.

This fact has implications related to the sovereignty of states over the sea and the right to exploit maritime resources accordingly the tradition and law established in the 17th to 19th centuries.

Safeguard measures adopted by several States:

- restrict the concept of freedom of the seas subject to a complex of the following restrictions:

a) The ideological conflict that involves the two superpowers (and their allies), both with nuclear power to destroy each other;

b) The political-economic conflict between more or less developed countries, which tends to unfavourably spread to the great powers the political and psychosocial repercussions of aggression against the less powerful; and

c) The technological evolution, which has allowed the less powerful states to possess military means capable of complicate the naval activity of the great powers, at least

close to their coasts - a faculty obviously aided by the restrictions on the use of force, due to (a) and (b),

- The problem of freedom of the seas also presents another rather curious aspect:

André Beaufre called “indirect strategy”, whose basic idea can be summarized as follows: the field of international relations is a battlefield in which, due to the military standoff, the objectives are pursued by indirect means, which always fall short of the use of military force.

The indirect strategy involves a wide range of activities, namely: diplomatic actions (including the pressures of armed diplomacy); economic actions (aid, quotas, boycotts, embargoes); clandestine actions (encouragement of subversion, revolutionary wars, “coups d'état”); psychosocial actions (advertising); and military interventions and limited wars.

In summary: In the nuclear age, an interaction between states occurs at the operational level of the Cold War, with sporadic spills into the hot level of limited employment of conventional military forces.

Excluding nuclear deterrence, the pressure on international relations is exerted today by secondary components of national powers, at least as regards the great powers.

Now, in the current strategic environment of permanent confrontation, but in which there is no direct war between the great powers, how to resolve the domain of the Sea or its denial of the enemy with the preservation of the freedom of the seas?

This preservation leads to the right to free shipping by all means of support for subversion and revolutionary wars (from ideology to missiles); the right to use political pressure by naval means; the right to use information (interception of communications) vessels; to the right of immersive position among others.

It is obvious, then, that in the confrontation of indirect strategy, maintaining the concept of freedom of the seas leads to the degradation of the idea of Sea domain, or its denial to the enemy, and vice versa.

Indeed, once the decision to establish the Sea domain, or to deny it to the enemy, is admitted, how much dominance or denial could be achieved without trigger the military escalation?

The answer to this question depends on many factors, including the interests involved and the risk, such as the Cuban missile crisis; This is a very difficult answer, particular for each situation and geographical area.

The sanctuary status that the sea has enjoyed in the limited conflicts of recent years reflects this difficulty: it is easier to respect the concept of freedom of the seas than to assess exactly how far can reach the degree of Sea domain or its denial.

Modern technology offers excellent opportunities for the pursuit of naval activities of the kind advocated by the conceptions of attrition and the French Young School, both suitable for states with limited naval power and maritime interests.

This technology also favours the exercise of covert naval activities, a fact that cannot be disregarded, because in the limited wars the political and psychosocial aspects of the problem can make awkward the retaliation for covert activities.

Mining, for example, is an operation that is difficult to accurately assign to a state and is very useful for denying Sea domain in restricted areas. Although the origin (manufacture) of mines can be easily defined, the identification of national responsibility for mining itself is much more difficult as it can be performed by submarines, aircraft, merchant ships and even small coast vessels.

Submarine actions are also not easy to pinpoint precisely in terms of national responsibility. It is natural that a force in warfare tends to regard all unidentified submarines detected in its surrounding area as hostile.

The ability to identify submerged submarines is a naval requirement that is challenging contemporary science and technology.

The small, fast and well-armed units are good tools for temporarily denying the Sea domain near the coast from which they operate.

In limited and intervention wars the State that needs to deploy its military power in the conflict area across the sea needs:

- (a) Suitable naval means for carrying out amphibious assaults (specialized ships, helicopters and various vessels);
- (b) Airborne means for predicting air support in amphibious assaults and for ground operations; and
- c) Means of transport capable of providing a continuous flow of logistical support.

For air support the use of UAVs such as RQ-21A Blackjack, MQ-8B Fire Scout, X-47B UCAV and TX concept ship.

Another relevant aspect that is raised is the use of cyber warfare in the naval context.

It is hard to imagine the Navy, for example the US, as the best in the world in cyber warfare, while at the same time being the best in the world in maritime warfare.

Similarly, few Marines would describe themselves as deeply in love with cyber warfare.

The delicate and distant nature of cyber warfare conflicts with the culture of close and personal combat.

As a Singular Force, the Cyber Force may provide contingents for each of the combatant commands in the form of a Component Command to operate. Having a cyber force is much simpler and more efficient than having existing Singular Forces contribute to CYBERCOM, which has to improvise cyber units and hand them over to combatants later.

This point will be described later in another Paper.

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